

Description and disclaimer

The downloadable data file (research_data_water_pollution_covid-19.csv) contains information on the measured Sodium (Na⁺), Potassium (K⁺), Calcium (Ca²⁺), Magnesium (Mg²⁺) and Chlorine (Cl⁻) amounts in mg/L in a precipitation amount in mm, and the reported COVID-19 cases and deaths in Austria. Each row contains the corresponding data for a certain day and per country. The dataset was generated using water_pollution_covid.py Python code.

You may use the generated research data in line with CC0 1.0:

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The Python code has CC BY 4.0 license:

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Source and licenses

The measured Natrium, Potassium, Calcium, Magnesium and Chlorine amounts in mg/L in a precipitation amount in mm were provided in a research called “Concentrations of major ions in wet precipitation samples in Austria”, its DOI is: 10.48436/b0g4h-rv840

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The reported COVID-19 cases and deaths were used from the following dataset:

<https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/data-daily-new-cases-covid-19-eueea-country>

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Title: Data on the daily number of new reported COVID-19 cases and deaths by EU/EEA country

Author: [European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control](#)

Source: <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/data-daily-new-cases-covid-19-eueea-country>

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Variable	Definition	Code
Date	Date of reporting “dd/mm/yyyy”	string
NS	Precipitation amount in mm	float64
Na	Concentration Na ⁺ in mg/L	float64
K	Concentration K ⁺ in mg/L	float64
Ca	Concentration Ca ²⁺ in mg/L	float64
Mg	Concentration Mg ²⁺ in mg/L	float64
Cl	Concentration Cl ⁻ in mg/L	float64
cases	Number of newly reported cases	int64
deaths	Number of newly reported deaths	int64